

Photocatalytic Graphene:TiO₂ Nanocomposites for Air Purification

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Abstract

Recently, Graphene and its composites are extensively explored by researchers for promising applications in the fields of energy, environment decontamination, energy storage, solar cells and photocatalyst [1-5] etc. The high electric charge carrier mobility, optical transparency, large surface area, easy chemical functionalization and mechanical strength with flexibility properties of graphene has made it as an ideal mechanical support, photo sensitizers and catalysts for nanocomposites development with enhanced performance depending upon the synergetic effects of components. In this work, graphene (G), TiO₂ nanoparticles (TN) and TiO₂ nanoparticles dispersed graphene nanocomposites (TG NC) have been prepared by chemical route for air purification. The structural, morphological, optical and vibrational properties of these powdered samples were characterized by using various analytical techniques to confirm their formation. The decontamination of polluted air by G, TN and TG NC reveals that TG NC is better than G and TN due to higher adsorptivity of contaminants and contaminant decomposition.

Keywords: Nanocomposite, graphene, TiO₂, Photocatalyst, Air Purification

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